

ID	Repositório	Linguagem	LOC	Quant. Arquivos	Star	Colaboradores	Total Nº Issues	Issues Status - Reopened		
								Total	Com comentários	Nº comentários
1	akka/akka	Scala	480931	2876	10144	647	14475	337	314	3487
2	antirez/redis	C	169449	673	37689	303	6208	97	73	629
3	ariya/phantomjs	HTML	49807	565	26906	134	5800	122	98	1037
4	AutoMapper/AutoMapper	C#	50744	611	6485	126	3148	92	88	1168
5	bartaz/impress.js	JavaScript	14782	73	34961	65	735	23	18	227
6	beanstalkd/beanstalkd (kr/beanstalkd)	C	8654	43	5150	52	476	7	7	86
7	bitcoin/bitcoin	C++	402185	1498	39435	637	16077	593	566	7995
8	boto/boto	Python	82452	675	6332	483	3866	56	39	231
9	cakephp/cakephp	PHP	193521	1276	7909	528	13343	398	374	4001
10	Compass/compass (chriseppstein/compass)	CSS	29095	762	6910	190	2149	76	68	984
11	d3/d3 (mbostock/d3)	JavaScript	2404	9	86178	122	1085	13	8	53
12	diaspora/diaspora	Ruby	160219	1780	12261	341	6996	222	211	3247
13	divio/django-cms	Python	164250	847	6909	391	6700	131	116	1051
14	django-debug-toolbar/django-debug-toolbar	Python	12432	114	5516	181	1168	30	27	213
15	django/django	Python	496424	3643	42949	1773	11519	174	139	1373
16	elasticsearch/elasticsearch	Java	1603394	13381	42876	1241	44074	973	892	8755
17	EllisLab/CodeIgniter	PHP	37085	314	17475	440	5797	150	123	1347
18	facebook/facebook-android-sdk	Java	67860	737	4879	70	280	6	2	7
19	facebook/folly	C++	303594	1676	13363	449	1186	37	36	248
20	facebook/hhvm (facebook/hiphop-php)	C++	1486055	29015	16096	632	8462	293	280	2769
21	facebook/tornado	Python	27992	166	18054	307	2702	44	39	223
22	FortAwesome/Font-Awesome	JavaScript	198167	3032	60436	6	15199	397	342	6266
23	ginatrapani/ThinkUp	PHP	145779	1065	3371	95	2285	46	30	203
24	github/android(pockethub/PocketHub)	Java	31353	703	9432	114	1239	32	23	235
25	gitlabhq/gitlabhq	Ruby	1519613	13587	21925	1942	3605	105	91	1123
26	h5bp/html5-boilerplate	JavaScript	9491	32	43109	231	2119	68	63	881
27	hadley/devtools	R	6092	99	1822	119	2067	60	56	402
28	harvesthq/chosen	HTML	14900	39	22118	100	3057	111	98	1017
29	hbons/SparkleShare	C#	19524	152	4255	142	1904	106	101	1234
30	Homebrew/legacy-homebrew (mxcl/homebrew)	Ruby	0	0	28065	5439	50645	1.102	1.029	12.968
31	imathis/octopress	Ruby	3667	92	9507	111	1786	57	50	387
32	JakeWharton/ActionBarSherlock	Java	34385	434	7251	53	1134	8	5	69
33	jkbr/httpie	Python	4440	54	42408	74	775	28	28	219
34	johnmylewhite/ProjectTemplate	R	5462	117	546	18	294	17	15	115
35	joyent/libuv	C	1	1	3327	0	1604	55	50	652
36	jquery/jquery	JavaScript	61046	255	51941	275	4367	181	166	2038
37	keithw/mosh	C++	15686	144	8481	60	1054	46	44	830
38	libgit2/libgit2	C	216426	1044	7058	368	5100	68	66	705
39	liuliu/ccv	C	234105	415	6515	9	216	4	4	29
40	mangos/MaNGOS	Markdown	951	3	2489	76	126	12	10	42
41	memcached/memcached	C	27957	161	9072	133	498	11	9	57
42	midgetspy/Sick-Beard	Python	88061	411	3067	126	989	18	13	87
43	mitsuhiko/flask	Python	10274	102	45505	546	3293	108	97	781
44	mojombo/jekyll	Ruby	37608	498	38250	857	7617	250	231	2996
45	mongodb/mongo	C++	4871492	22633	16395	386	1298	34	25	124
46	mono/mono	C#	9275202	52228	8026	690	15507	250	221	2025
47	moxiecode/plupload	JavaScript	14998	94	5223	52	1594	51	38	278

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48	mrdoob/three.js	JavaScript	451333	2933	53318	1115	17053	428	398	4403
49	NancyFx/Nancy	C#	79077	1139	6815	265	2971	81	70	736
50	nathanmarz/storm	Java	67989	569	9046	42	304	8	5	69
51	netty/netty	Java	288089	2633	20087	385	9281	292	281	3853
52	node-v0.x-archive (joyent/node)	JavaScript	12	3	35439	2	10182	405	395	4659
53	nodejs/http-parser (joyent/http-parser)	C	6251	9	4828	77	485	7	6	30
54	openframeworks/openFrameworks	C++	230875	1531	7105	285	6305	176	164	2362
55	plataformatec/devise	Ruby	13190	248	20040	541	5084	133	121	1088
56	psf/requests (kennethreitz/requests)	Python	8566	56	39488	537	4889	262	230	3593
57	rails/rails	Ruby	333500	3520	43695	3841	36493	1.287	1219	15028
58	ravendb/ravendb	C#	751003	5896	2271	241	9066	65	27	82
59	reddit/reddit	Python	162431	763	15053	179	891	21	19	167
60	restSharp/RestSharp	C#	15465	176	6504	188	1328	46	40	378
61	robey/kestrel	Scala	12562	77	2803	23	152	1	1	2
62	rstudio/shiny	R	69746	321	3466	44	2529	52	45	315
63	SamSaffron/MiniProfiler	Markdown	5	3	1077	75	200	2	2	16
64	sbt/sbt	Scala	53227	1121	3885	205	4781	165	151	1558
65	scala/scala	Scala	340732	7577	11912	444	1748	291	272	4006
66	scalatra/scalatra	Scala	16365	262	2401	100	946	17	14	57
67	sebastianbergmann/phpunit	PHP	164813	681	14416	363	3750	94	88	828
68	ServiceStack/ServiceStack	C#	376873	2996	4512	248	844	11	10	45
69	SignalR/SignalR	C#	203515	1046	7761	78	4380	178	154	1343
70	symfony/symfony	PHP	739186	7317	21243	1902	32113	730	669	7658
71	thoughtbot/paperclip	Ruby	15839	161	9053	370	2644	77	70	1023
72	TrinityCore/TrinityCore	C++	1842842	12958	5502	367	23168	1.282	1189	13275
73	twitter/finagle	Scala	141521	1718	7198	243	777	23	21	241
74	twitter/flockdb	Scala	6479	75	3200	12	50	1	1	3
75	twitter/zipkin	Java	111657	680	11359	79	2694	48	41	480
76	vmg/redcarpet	C	7913	73	4429	95	675	18	17	100
77	xbmc/xbmc	C++	970830	6054	9358	641	16331	292	273	4655
78	yihui/knitr	R	11178	179	1807	120	1732	52	44	379
79	zendframework/zendframework (zendframework/zf2)	Markdown	4010	9	5713	666	7777	292	239	2107
80	zurb/foundation-sites (zurb/foundation)	HTML	117167	620	28119	983	11688	341	297	3405
Total			30304250	221533	1330974	35890	506227	14277	12996	152838
Média			378803	2769	16637	449	6328	178	162	1910
Desvio padrão			1194604	7359	16965	795	9542	269	252	3046